

The Development of Third-Party Punishment and Reward in ni-Vanuatu Children: Evidence of Cost-Benefit Calculations

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Author statement

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Abstract

20

21 This study examined third-party punishment and reward in 303 ni-Vanuatu children (282 urban,
22 21 rural; aged 4-11 years) responding to property destruction by an antisocial actor. By age 5, a
23 majority preferentially punished the antisocial vs. the neutral actor. Whereas punishment of antisocial
24 behaviour increased with age in our sample, prior research in a similar ni-Vanuatu sample found
25 decreasing punishment of unfairness with age, suggesting that different norm violations evoke distinct
26 developmental trajectories. Children demonstrated strategic decision-making: punishment increased
27 when it was free of economic or social cost. Unexpectedly, rewarding the antisocial actor was
28 common among younger children, and decreased with age, occurred more frequently when in-person,
29 and was associated with punishing the neutral actor – patterns consistent with appeasement of
30 perceived dominant individuals and competitive status assertion towards weaker individuals. Cross-
31 cultural and cross-community comparisons revealed similar punishment rates between urban ni-
32 Vanuatu and Swedish children, and between urban and rural ni-Vanuatu children. In context of the
33 literature, the results suggest early development of punitive tendencies may be human universal.
34 However, the prevalence of rewarding of antisocial individuals, and cultural differences revealed by
35 other studies, still raise important questions about how culturally evolved punishment behaviours
36 interact with core cognitive and motivational processes during development.

37 Keywords

38 Moral development; Norm enforcement; Third-party punishment; Cross-cultural psychology;
39 Cost-benefit decision-making; Reward; Appeasement; Competition for status

40

Introduction

41

42 People from a wide range of societies exhibit preferences for punishment in response to norm
43 violations (reviewed in Molho et al., 2024). This has massive consequences for societies – for
44 example in the USA, approaching 1% of adults are incarcerated by the criminal justice system at any
45 given time (Sawyer & Wagner, 2025). Experimental studies indicate that while second-party
46 punishment (i.e., punishment carried out by the victims of the norm transgression) shows little cross-
47 cultural variation, third-party punishment (i.e., punishment carried out by unaffected bystanders of
48 the norm transgression) tends to increase with community and ethnic group size (Henrich et al., 2006;
49 Marlowe et al., 2008). Anthropological observations of real-world behaviours often appear to support
50 this pattern, as third-party punishment (3PP) tends to be rare in small-scale, rural societies (Singh &
51 Garfield, 2022; Wiessner, 2005, 2020), and associated with higher levels of population density,
52 warfare, and social stratification/complexity (Garfield et al., 2023; Jackson et al., 2020; Spitzer,
53 1975). This body of evidence led to the conclusion that the cost-benefit trade-off for third-party
54 punishers varies across societies: in small-scale egalitarian societies, the costs of 3PP – such as
55 severed social ties in close-knit communities – often outweigh the benefits, making alternative
56 strategies (such as third-party mediation and compensation of victims) more adaptive. In contrast, in
57 large-scale, socially stratified societies, the benefits of 3PP – such as enforcement of social norms –
58 can more easily outweigh the costs (Wiessner, 2005; Molho et al., 2024). Cross-cultural differences
59 and similarities are used to support complex arguments about the evolutionary and cultural roots of
60 3PP (Baumard, 2010; Bowles & Gintis, 2004; Fehr et al., 2002; Guala, 2012; Gintis, 2000; Smith,
61 2020). These discussions also consider the extent to which punishment decisions appear strategic with
62 respect to issues relevant for personal interest, such as the possibility of retaliation by the punished
63 party (Lee et al., 2024; Molho et al., 2020; Molho & Wu, 2021).

64 Development of 3PP

65 Information about developmental patterns of 3PP can be highly relevant for informing such
66 discussions, especially if cross-cultural. Developmental trajectories which are initially similar across
67 societies but later diverge can be indicative of both human universals and cultural evolutionary
68 processes (Amir & McAuliffe, 2020; Henrich et al., 2010). Until recently (and when the current study
69 was conducted), almost no such information was available for 3PP. The purpose of this study was
70 therefore to provide a single example of the development of 3PP in a non-WEIRD (Henrich et al.,
71 2010) society – Vanuatu in Melanesia – focussing on the effects of different types of costs.
72 Fortuitously, since data was collected, Vanuatu has emerged as an outlier in a large cross-cultural
73 study of 3PP development (McAuliffe et al., 2025). From a very broad selection of six countries
74 across five continents, Vanuatu was the only society where children became progressively less
75 selective with age when allocating 3PP to fair versus unfair agents, and one of only two (with Uganda)
76 where 3PP did not increase with age. This is particularly notable in the context of a second cross-
77 cultural study of the development of 3PP of unfairness also conducted in six different cultures, none
78 of which showed such a diminished selectivity, and all of which showed an increase in 3PP with age
79 (House et al., 2020). Another study conducted across eight diverse societies also found a universal
80 tendency for children to enforce conventional norms (Kanngiesser et al., 2022).

81 Despite the near universality across many societies of the developmental emergence of norm
82 enforcement, some important variation was observed. The magnitude of enforcement varied across
83 societies, with no clear relationship to community size (Kanngiesser et al., 2022). Conversely, the
84 style of verbal interventions clearly varied depending on community size: in small-scale societies,
85 imperative protests (e.g., “don’t do it”) were more common than rule protests (referring to the specific
86 rule being broken), whereas in large-scale societies, both protest types occurred with similar
87 frequency. In contrast, the style of non-verbal interventions (actions, gestures, body contact) varied
88 more widely across societies, without a consistent pattern (Kanngiesser et al., 2022).

89 Our results both clarify and complicate the cross-cultural developmental picture by further
90 illuminating the development of 3PP in Vanuatu. We examined 3PP responses to a type of norm
91 violation – property destruction – that has not yet to our knowledge been tested in non-WEIRD
92 developmental contexts (with one exemption from Colombia involving virtual property destruction
93 in a digital environment, Arini et al., 2023). Most developmental studies on 3PP have used fairness
94 violations in resource distributions, including all large-scale cross-cultural studies of moral violations
95 (House et al., 2020; McAuliffe et al., 2025). Before we describe our study, we provide a further
96 overview of previous research on the development of 3PP, which has been conducted extensively in
97 urban contexts in Europe and North America (Amir & McAuliffe, 2020; Nielsen et al., 2017), with
98 relevant evidence available from early in life.

99 Eight-month-old infants and 19-month-old toddlers from the US prefer those who punish
100 antisocial individuals over those who act prosocially towards them (Hamlin et al., 2011, Experiments
101 2-3). Ten-month-old Swedish infants prefer to watch an unfair rather than a fair individual being
102 punished (Meristo & Surian, 2014). Swedish children as young as four advocate for punishment of
103 antisocial individuals, even when doing so requires deviating from actions demonstrated by adults
104 (Kenward & Östh, 2012). Six-year-old German children are willing to give up their own resources to
105 observe an antisocial individual being punished (Mendes et al., 2018). During middle childhood,
106 children begin to use 3PP to enforce norms about a variety of moral domains, including care, equity,
107 loyalty, authority, ownership and freedom, with different behaviours and developmental trajectories
108 sometimes evident for different domains (Arini et al., 2023, 2025; see also the review by Marshall &
109 McAuliffe, 2022). As children grow older, their 3PP rates tend to increase (House et al., 2020; Jordan
110 et al., 2014; McAuliffe et al., 2015, 2025; Salali et al., 2015), while their 3PP severity decreases
111 (Gummerum et al., 2009; Arini et al., 2021, 2025). Boys have been shown to engage in 3PP more
112 frequently than girls in a Swedish sample (Kenward & Östh, 2015).

113 There is evidence that carrying out 3PP may have emotional costs for children (Arini et al., 2021,
114 2025; Marshall et al., 2021; but see Arini et al., 2023). However, research about the effects of cost on

115 children's propensity to engage in 3PP has been mostly focused on economic costs. Similarly to what
116 has been observed in adults (Lewisch et al., 2011; Fan et al., 2013), economic cost reduces children's
117 3PP rates, thus indicating that children are also capable of strategic cost-benefit calculations. For
118 instance, from 6 years of age, US children have been found to punish selfish players in sharing games
119 by preventing them from receiving valuable resources (candies). However, they were more likely to
120 do so when punishment came at no personal cost than when it required sacrificing part of their own
121 candy endowment (McAuliffe et al., 2015). A similar pattern was observed in 4- to 10-year-old US
122 children who witnessed free riding rather than selfishness: children were more likely to punish free
123 riders by taking away their resources when doing so was non-costly, compared to when it involved
124 forfeiting a desirable resource (sticker) (Yang et al., 2018). The effect was surprisingly in the opposite
125 direction in Ugandan children, who were more likely to punish selfish individuals when it was costly,
126 perhaps because they only felt licensed to punish when having a stake in the situation, whereas ni-
127 Vanuatu, Indian and Peruvian children showed no sensitivity to punishment costs (McAuliffe et al.,
128 2025).

129 Researchers have begun examining whether the economic cost of punishment influences
130 children's intergroup biases in 3PP decisions, with particular attention to two types of biases: the
131 ingroup policing bias (i.e., greater tendency to punish ingroup than outgroup norm violators) and the
132 ingroup protectionism bias (i.e., greater tendency to punish norm violators who victimise ingroup
133 than outgroup members). Studies with 6- to 11-year-old Argentinian and 3- to 6-year-old US children
134 show different patterns: in Argentinian children, ingroup protectionism appeared only in costly
135 punishment, while ingroup policing emerged in both costly and non-costly conditions (Gonzalez-
136 Gadea et al., 2022). By comparison, US children showed ingroup policing only in costly punishment
137 (Yudkin et al., 2020). These differences suggest cultural, methodological, or developmental factors
138 influence how punishment costs affect intergroup biases, with biases typically emerging when
139 motivation overcomes costs.

140 To our knowledge, only one study to date has explored whether costs other than economic
141 influence children's tendency to engage in 3PP. Specifically, Kenward and Östh (2015)
142 operationalised cost in social terms, as the risk of retaliation from the punished norm violator. This
143 was arguably a more naturalistic manipulation since the risk of retaliation has been highlighted as one
144 of the crucial factors that adults consider when deciding which punishment type to enact in real life
145 interactions (Molho et al., 2020; Molho & Wu, 2021). It was found that, when asked to decide between
146 punishing or rewarding antisocial and neutral adults (by allocating them bad or good sweets,
147 respectively), 5-year-old Swedish children preferred to punish the antisocial adult and reward the
148 neutral actor. Importantly, children's preference for punishing antisocial adults was stronger when
149 3PP was to be administered anonymously (when there was no risk of retaliation) rather than in-person.
150 However, a limitation in Kenward and Östh's (2015) methodology is that children's choice to allocate
151 the bad sweets could reflect a general avoidance of rewarding antisocial individuals, not necessarily
152 an intention to punish, because children experienced a forced choice between allocating good or bad
153 sweets.

154 The current study tests whether these findings replicate in ni-Vanuatu children, addressing this
155 shortcoming by modifying Kenward and Östh's (2015) design to give children the possibility to
156 choose among three alternative item allocations to each actor. We included bad sweets, as per the
157 original design, to give children the opportunity to punish. We added an empty box, to give children
158 the opportunity to choose a neutral outcome. We used good sweets, as per the original design, for
159 exploratory reasons – although not an initial theoretical focus, we thought it possible there might be
160 interesting allocation patterns, for example, allocation of good sweets to the antisocial actor might
161 represent appeasement. This is known in children (Charafeddine et al., 2016; Keltner et al., 1997),
162 though see Lee et al. (2024) for a counterexample in a relevant context. Because of obtained results,
163 we have a post-hoc focus on this very possibility, and therefore model allocation of good sweets in
164 the same way as allocation of bad sweets.

165 We examined whether children would preferentially punish the norm violator (i.e., antisocial
166 actor), as observed in several previous studies of WEIRD children (e.g., Hamlin et al., 2011; Jordan
167 et al., 2014; Kenward & Östh, 2015; McAuliffe et al., 2015) (RQ1 in Table 1). We investigated the
168 earliest age at which children preferentially punish the antisocial actor (RQ2 in Table 1), predicting
169 that this would occur by five years of age (Kenward & Östh, 2015).

170 Moreover, we manipulated both economic and social costs to examine their effects on 3PP of
171 norm violators in children (RQ3-4 in Table 1). Economic cost was operationalised as requiring
172 children to sacrifice part of their own sweet endowment to enact 3PP, similarly to the protocols
173 adopted by McAuliffe et al. (2015) and later by Gonzalez-Gadea et al. (2022) and McAuliffe et al.
174 (2025). Social cost, instead, was operationalised as initially informing children they would deliver
175 their 3PP decisions in person rather than anonymously, as previously implemented by Kenward and
176 Östh (2015). We originally expected to replicate the findings that children's 3PP rates are lower when
177 3PP is (socially and economically) costly compared to when it is (socially and economically) non-
178 costly (Kenward & Östh, 2015; McAuliffe et al., 2015). However, the part of this prediction about
179 the economic cost manipulation is challenged by the results of McAuliffe et al. (2025), which showed
180 no effect of economic cost on 3PP rates in ni-Vanuatu children.

181 Additionally, we examined the effects of age and gender on 3PP rates (RQ5-6 in Table 1),
182 predicting that 3PP rates would be higher in older (vs. younger) children and in boys (vs. girls), in
183 line with previous literature (effect of age: Jordan et al., 2014; McAuliffe et al., 2015; Salali et al.,
184 2015, but see McAuliffe et al., 2025; effect of gender: Kenward & Östh, 2015). Because we tested
185 children across a wide age range (4 to 11 years), we also intended to investigate whether and how the
186 effects of gender, economic and social costs on 3PP rates change over the course of childhood (RQ7-
187 9 in Table 1). However, because the decision to add an economically costly condition was made after
188 data collection was already begun, less data was obtained in that condition, and so although power
189 was sufficient to examine main effects of economic cost, we could not reasonably expect to examine
190 the interaction with age.

191 Since our protocol was adapted from Kenward and Östh (2015), this enabled comparison of 3PP
 192 rates between urban ni-Vanuatu and urban Swedish children using the original Swedish data
 193 (available in Figure 2 of Kenward & Östh, 2015) (RQ10 in Table 1), but we had no strong predictions
 194 for this comparison. We further examined whether urban and rural ni-Vanuatu children would differ
 195 in their propensity to punish antisocial individuals (RQ11 in Table 1). We originally predicted that
 196 3PP rates would be higher in the urban sample, as it was characterised by higher community and
 197 ethnic group size than the rural sample (Henrich et al., 2006; Marlowe et al., 2008). This prediction
 198 is heavily strengthened by the results of McAuliffe et al. (2025) who found marked differences in line
 199 with this.

200 The research questions and associated predictions listed in Table 1 were formed a priori in
 201 advance of data analysis. They were not preregistered because data collection was started in 2013,
 202 when the practice was less standard. The a priori research questions related to allocation of bad sweets
 203 (punishment); analysis of allocation of the good sweets (reward) is exploratory.

204

205 *Table 1.* Summary of a priori research questions, associated predictions and whether they were
 206 supported in the present study.

207

Research Question	Prediction	Outcome
RQ1: Do children preferentially punish the antisocial (vs. neutral) actor?	Children allocate 3PP (bad sweets) more often to the antisocial actor than the neutral actor (based on much previous research).	Prediction supported.
RQ2: When do children start to preferentially punish the antisocial (vs. neutral) actor?	Children allocate 3PP (bad sweets) more often to the antisocial actor than the neutral actor by age 5 (Kenward & Östh, 2015).	Prediction supported.
RQ3: Does economic cost influence 3PP rates?	Children enact 3PP more often when it is economically non-costly than costly (McAuliffe et al., 2015).	Prediction supported.
RQ4: Does social cost influence 3PP rates?	Children enact 3PP more often when it is socially non-costly than costly (Kenward & Östh, 2015).	Prediction supported.
RQ5: Does age influence 3PP rates?	Children enact 3PP more often the older they get (Jordan et al., 2014; McAuliffe et al., 2015; Salali et al., 2015).	Prediction supported.
RQ6: Does gender influence 3PP rates?	Boys enact 3PP more often than girls (Kenward & Östh, 2015).	No detected effect.
RQ7: Does age moderate any effect of social cost on 3PP rates?	No prediction.	Yes, social cost only influences at intermediate ages.

RQ8: Does age moderate any effect of gender on 3PP rates?	No prediction.	No moderation detected.
RQ9: Does age moderate any effect of economic cost on 3PP rates?	No prediction.	Economic cost sample too small to test moderation.
RQ10: Are there differences in 3PP rates between urban ni-Vanuatu and Swedish children?	No prediction.	No detected effect.
RQ11: Are there differences in 3PP rates between rural and urban children in Vanuatu?	Urban children enact 3PP more often than rural children (Henrich et al., 2006; Marlowe et al., 2008).	No detected effect.

208

209 Socio-economic and Cultural Context in Vanuatu

210 Social and cultural insights into the society of our ni-Vanuatu samples came from in-depth
 211 ethnographic fieldwork carried out by one of the team's researchers (HD), who was fluent in *Bislama*.
 212 Vanuatu is an archipelago consisting of 83 islands (of which between 60-70 are inhabited), part of
 213 Melanesia, located in the southwestern Pacific Ocean. Two of its largest islands are Efate (where the
 214 capital Port Vila is located) and Tanna, which differ in socio-economic and various cultural aspects.
 215 Data collection was conducted in Port Vila (Vanuatu's capital city located on the southwestern coast
 216 of Efate) and in the rural region of *Niprainitata* (in the southeastern part of Tanna), resting underneath
 217 the highly active Mt. Yasur volcano.

218 *Community Size.* At the time of data collection, Efate had a population of approximately 65,700
 219 people, the majority of which (44,000 circa) resided in Port Vila, while the rest lived in a number of
 220 'areas', villages and settlements. Tanna had a significantly smaller population, with approximately
 221 28,800 inhabitants spread across multiple villages (Vanuatu National Statistics Office, 2010). The
 222 *Niprainitata* region contained around 40 small village clusters of as few as 50, to 300 individuals,
 223 spread across a network of interconnected *nakamals*, as estimated during our fieldwork. In this region,
 224 the traditional *nakamal* (customary community meeting place) is a wide, circular, ashen dancing
 225 ground next to a large banyan tree, with accompanying structures for preparing food, kava,
 226 conducting meetings and ritual processes.

227 *Language, Culture and Religion.* *Kastom* comes from the word custom (Crowley, 2003), used
 228 throughout Vanuatu to describe traditional practices, values and beliefs. Rhetorically, it is often used
 229 in contrast to aspects of modernity, and is strongly associated with land, daily living, traditional rites
 230 and titles, and any of the 113 different Austronesian languages spoken throughout the archipelago. In
 231 Port Vila, the primary languages spoken were Bislama (a creole combining English, French, and
 232 indigenous vocabulary with a Melanesian grammar and syntax), alongside English and French, as a
 233 result of the country's colonial history (Crowley, 1990; Tryon, 1999). The rural communities of
 234 Tanna, instead, used a combination of Bislama and indigenous languages called vernaculars (Willans,
 235 2013) such as Kwamera, Whitesands and Lenakel (François et al., 2015). The region in question,
 236 *Niprainitata*, spoke *Nafe* (Dixson, 2016). Christianity was the dominant religion across both regions,
 237 though on Tanna customary beliefs were also practised (Vanuatu National Statistics Office, 2010).

238 *Economic Organisation.* The main source of household income varied substantially between
 239 urban and rural areas: the economic base of urban Port Vila was primarily wage labour, while rural
 240 Tanna's economy was predominantly dependent on subsistence farming. More specifically, at the
 241 time of data collection, in Port Vila 82.0% of households relied on wages/salary; 6.5% on their own
 242 business; and only 2.2% on the sale of fish, crops or handicrafts. In contrast, in the region of Tanna
 243 61.0% of households relied on the sale of fish, crops or handicrafts; 12.7% on wages/salary; and 9.5%
 244 on their own business (Vanuatu National Statistics Office, 2010). Regardless of geographic context,
 245 across Vanuatu most communities (including many urban ones) engage in horticulture in large
 246 'gardens' that could also be described as 'food forests' (Dixson, 2016).

247 *Social Structure.* In the rural communities of Tanna, descent (i.e., membership in a lineage/clan)
 248 and land inheritance followed patrilineal transmission, namely both were passed on by fathers to sons.
 249 Moreover, patrilocal post-marital residence on Tanna was the norm, meaning that women moved to
 250 live with their husband's family upon marriage (Lindstrom, 1985). In contrast, communities in Efate
 251 had historically followed a matrilineal system, under which descent and land inheritance traced
 252 through women. In other words, children belonged to their mother's lineage, not their father's. Land

253 was passed through women too, but their brothers acted as land “administrators”. Therefore, decision-
254 making about land was *de facto* transmitted from mother’s brother to sister’s son (Naupa & Simo,
255 2008). However, in Port Vila, various social influences including Christianisation, land
256 commoditisation, and significant inter-island migration have changed this system. Nowadays, both
257 men and women can inherit land and exercise decision-making power over it; women may lease land
258 in their own name or enter into joint leases with their husbands. However, tenure of leased land in the
259 city is governed more by cash availability than by kinship-based obligations (Naupa & Simo, 2008).
260 Finally, based on our field observations, post-marital residence patterns in Port Vila are increasingly
261 mixed, with cases of patrilocality, matrilocality (i.e., husbands moving to their wives’ family
262 households), and neolocality (i.e., couples establishing new, independent households separate from
263 both families). Port Vila is a centre of inter-island trade and migration, with a number of areas
264 described as ‘*miks aelen*’ or mixed island communities absorbing customs from across the
265 archipelago. Consequently, children in Port Vila are often born to interisland relationships and live in
266 culturally heterogeneous urban settlements exposed to much more transnational influences (Dixson
267 et al., 2018), as well as better resourced schooling. However, outside of formal schooling, in Port Vila
268 only 19% of a group of 62 child interviewees were able to speak an indigenous language, and about
269 half of another group (n = 127) were raised in exclusive Bislama-speaking households (Dixson,
270 2016). With *kastom* transmitted through home-island language, this is a notable contrast regarding
271 their early socialisation.

272 *Education.* Vanuatu’s formal education system had 2 years of pre-school, 6 at primary level
273 (starting at 6 years of age), 4 for lower secondary, and 3 for upper secondary (Education Profiles,
274 n.d.). Education levels were higher in Port Vila than in rural areas of Tanna. At the time of data
275 collection, in Port Vila, 14.9% of the general population (aged 15 and above) had not completed
276 primary education, 47.5% had completed primary but not secondary education, and 31.4% had
277 completed secondary education or higher. In contrast, in the rural areas of Tanna, 63.8% of the
278 population had not completed primary education, 22.1% had completed primary but not secondary

279 education, and only 6.0% had completed secondary education or higher (Vanuatu National Statistics
280 Office, 2010). Regarding less formal metrics, childhood involvement in household economy,
281 traditional ecological knowledge and customary practices is higher in rural Tanna than Port Vila. For
282 example, across 93 child interviews, 87 carried their own ‘bush knife’ and used it daily in gardens
283 and forests, while the majority of Port Vila based children did not (Dixson, 2016).

284 Methods

285 All measures, manipulations, and exclusions in the research are reported in the manuscript.

286 Participants

287 Sample size was determined by practical concerns: we collected as much data as possible in the
288 amount of time available over three field visits (September-October 2013; April-May 2014; August-
289 September 2014). In total, we collected data from 303 children by testing them face-to-face at their
290 schools. Of these 303 children, 282 lived in urban areas, specifically in Port Vila (mean age: 7.0 years;
291 SD age: 1.7 years; age range: 4.1–10.9 years; gender distribution: 145 girls and 137 boys), while the
292 remaining 21 lived in rural areas of Tanna’s *Niprainitata* region (mean age: 7.3 years; SD age:
293 1.1 years; age range: 5.5–9.9 years; gender distribution: 10 girls and 11 boys). All participants, both
294 urban and rural children, were ethnically Melanesian ni-Vanuatu. The participants were from the same
295 populations, tested during overlapping field seasons, and by the same fieldworker as the Vanuatu
296 samples from McAuliffe et al. (2025): all fieldwork and liaison work was carried out by author HD
297 as part of a larger collection of studies for his PhD thesis (Dixson, 2016).

298 Recruitment in Port Vila was conducted by sending invitation letters in Bislama to the parents of
299 children attending Port Vila Central School; all children attending this school lived in Port Vila.
300 Recruitment in rural southeast Tanna was conducted after having obtained verbal permission from a
301 traditional chiefly authority, as well as the principal, teachers and pupils of Iquarmanu Primary

302 School, and their parents. Children attending this school came from multiple villages across the
303 *Niprainitata* region.

304 The study was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of the Australian National
305 University (protocol 2012/218, study's title: "The Behavioural Ecology of Prosocial Behaviour in
306 Vanuatu") and received separate cultural approval from the Malvatumauri National Council of Chiefs
307 in Vanuatu.

308 Design

309 We operationalise *social cost* as an *anonymity* manipulation (with levels *in-person* vs.
310 *anonymous*). This applies to the circumstances under which children are led to expect they ultimately
311 will allocate the good or bad sweets or empty box. Social cost is thus operationalised for the bad
312 sweets allocation, but this manipulation obviously has a different implication for the other allocations.

313 The design matrix for urban children is somewhat unbalanced, chiefly in that the *economically*
314 *costly condition* was administered to fewer and younger children (Table 2). This was due to a late
315 decision to include this condition, and practical challenges of operating in the field leading to less
316 data than originally expected in the *economically costly condition*. Further, a decision was taken to
317 test all rural children in one condition (*anonymous, free-of-economic-cost*), because the sample size
318 was anticipated to be small. Our statistical models can deal with the unbalanced design, and we
319 present summary statistics adapted to this imbalance, i.e. focussing on model predictions rather than
320 raw summaries. Children were randomly assigned to either the *in-person* or *anonymous condition*. In
321 contrast, assignment to the *free-of-economic-cost* vs. *economically costly condition* was semi-
322 randomised, as children tested later were more likely to be in the *economically costly condition*.

323 *Table 2. Sample sizes of children in each between-subjects condition.*

Age	Urban				Rural
	Free of economic cost		Economically costly		Free of economic cost
	In person	Anonymous	In person	Anonymous	In person
4	8	12	5	7	0
5	25	22	9	8	1
6	20	30	8	7	9
7	10	26	0	0	6
8	25	13	0	0	2
9	15	23	0	1	3
10	3	5	0	0	0
Total	106	131	22	23	21

324

325

Materials

326 During the experiment, three small plastic containers with distinct coloured lids – red, green, and
327 white – were used. These containers either remained empty or contained sweets. The sweets were of
328 two types, good and bad. The lid colours for good and bad sweets were counterbalanced across
329 participants. Photographs of adult individuals depicted an antisocial actor and a neutral actor, who
330 respectively violated and abided by norms of social coexistence. For example, the antisocial actor
331 was pictured holding a torn shirt they were described as having destroyed. The gender of both actors
332 was matched to that of the participant. Large cardboard boxes were employed to display the photos
333 of the antisocial and neutral actors, as well as to hold the participant’s chosen plastic container.

334

Procedure

335 The protocol was adapted from a similar methodology developed by Kenward and Östh (2015).
336 A full script is available as supplementary material (Anon, 2026). The experiment was divided into
337 three phases: (1) sweet familiarisation, (2) third-party interaction, and (3) distribution task (full script
338 is available at a GitHub repository; Anon, 2026). During the **sweet familiarisation phase**, the
339 experimenter presented three small plastic containers to the participant: one container was empty,
340 another contained good sweets, and the remaining one contained bad sweets. The experimenter
341 demonstrated the difference between good and bad sweets by smelling them, under the pretext he had

342 forgotten which was which. The good sweets were described as smelling delicious and the bad sweets
343 as smelling disgusting. The plastic containers containing sweets had either a red or green lid, with the
344 lid colour counterbalanced across participants, while the empty container always had a white lid.
345 Once the experimenter presented the plastic containers, he arranged them in a line in front of the
346 participant and then asked them to recall the content of each container.

347 The **third-party interaction phase** involved a narrative accompanied by colour photographs
348 featuring real ni-Vanuatu people, either adult men (for boy participants) or women (for girl
349 participants). These photographs were sourced from a community development NGO called *Youth*
350 *Challenge International*. The events reported in the narrative were presented as real, as if they had
351 taken place somewhere far away. The narrative described a protagonist who had recently purchased
352 an item (a shirt for the male protagonist; a necklace for the female protagonist). At different times,
353 the protagonist encountered two individuals: a neutral and an antisocial actor. Both actors approached
354 the protagonist, commented on the new item they are wearing, and asked to have a closer look. The
355 neutral actor looked at the item and said that it was an alright shirt/necklace, before handing it back
356 to the protagonist. Instead, the antisocial actor destroyed the item, by tearing the shirt or breaking the
357 string holding the beads of the necklace. This required the protagonist to take the damaged item to a
358 group of *mamas* (respected female elders within the community), who repaired it by either sewing up
359 the shirt or re-threading the beads. The order of interactions between the protagonist and the antisocial
360 and neutral actors was counterbalanced across participants to control for potential order effects. At
361 the end of the narrative, participants were asked to identify which individual had destroyed the item
362 and which had not.

363 Following the narrative, the child participated in the **distribution task**. Two large cardboard
364 boxes were placed in front of the participant: one contained a photo of the antisocial actor, and the
365 other contained a photo of the neutral actor (Figure 1). The experimenter shuffled the cardboard boxes
366 without looking at them, thus remaining blind to their contents. Three small plastic containers (i.e.,
367 the same used during the familiarisation phase) were then placed in front of each cardboard box: an

368 empty container with a white lid, a container of good sweets with a red/green lid, and a container of
369 bad sweets with a green/red lid (six containers in total). The participant was instructed to open each
370 cardboard box and examine the photos inside without removing them. The experimenter then
371 explained that the participant needed to decide which of the three plastic containers to place in each
372 cardboard box, so that they could be delivered to the people depicted in the photos. This setup allowed
373 the participant to choose one of three outcomes for the antisocial and neutral actors: a neutral (empty
374 container), positive (container of good sweets) or negative outcome (container of bad sweets).
375 Notably, in Kenward and Östh's (2015) methodology, the participant could only choose between a
376 positive and a negative outcome for the antisocial and neutral actors; the neutral option was not
377 available.

378

379 *Figure 1.* Participant view during the distribution task.

380

381 Similarly to Kenward and Östh's (2015) methodology, we manipulated whether participants
382 believed they would assign the outcomes to the antisocial and neutral actors in person or
383 anonymously. In the *in-person condition*, the participant was told that the two individuals portrayed
384 in the photos would be coming by boat to visit their school. The child was informed that they would
385 have to personally deliver the boxes to these individuals. In the *anonymous condition*, the participant
386 was told the boxes would be sent to the individuals' community and placed in their bedrooms, where
387 they would find them without knowing who had sent them.

388 Differently from Kenward and Östh's (2015) methodology, we also manipulated whether
389 participants had to pay an economic cost when assigning the outcomes to the antisocial and neutral
390 actors (for a similar manipulation, see McAuliffe et al., 2015, 2025, and Gonzalez-Gadea et al., 2022).
391 In the *economically costly condition*, the participant was initially given an endowment of five good
392 sweets. For every allocation of a box containing sweets (to either the antisocial or the neutral actor),
393 the participant had to "pay" one sweet from their endowment. For example, if the participant decided
394 to send the neutral actor a box containing good sweets and the antisocial actor a box containing bad
395 sweets, they would lose two sweets of their own endowment (one sweet per allocation). Instead, in
396 the *free-of-economic-cost condition*, the participant did not receive an endowment, and sending any
397 boxes containing sweets did not require sacrificing their own resources. Notably, in both the
398 *economically costly* and *free-of-economic-cost conditions*, allocating the empty container required no
399 payment.

400 While the participant made their distribution decisions, the experimenter looked away, pretending
401 to be occupied with other work, ensuring he could not see the participant's choice. If he heard no
402 activity from the participant, the experimenter repeated the instructions. Once the participant
403 indicated they had completed the distribution task, they were instructed to close both cardboard boxes.

Results

404

405 Allocation of bad sweets (punishment)

406 The antisocial actor was allocated bad sweets by 49% of children, compared to 11% for the neutral
 407 actor, OR (odds ratio) = 7.4, 95% CI [4.8, 11.6], $p < .001$, Fisher's Exact Test (testing RQ1) (note that
 408 all raw data and analysis code is available at a GitHub repository, for permanent archive on
 409 manuscript acceptance, Anon, 2026). This difference was not clear when examining four-year-olds
 410 only (19% punished the antisocial actor, 9% the neutral, $n = 64$, OR = 2.2, 95% CI [0.4, 15.0], $p =$
 411 .474), but was clear when examining five-year-olds (31% compared to 11%, $n = 130$, OR = 3.6, 95%
 412 CI [1.3, 11.1], $p = .009$) and children six and older (60% compared to 12%, $n = 412$, OR = 10.7, 95%
 413 CI [6.3, 18.5], $p < .001$) (RQ2). Punishment of the antisocial actor was more common when allocation
 414 was free of economic cost (RQ3) and when allocation was anonymous (RQ4) (Figure 2, Table 3).
 415 Moreover, punishment of the antisocial actor increased with age (RQ5), but was not affected by
 416 children's gender (RQ6, Table 3). On the other hand, the rare behaviour of punishing the neutral actor
 417 (Figure 2) was unaffected by any manipulation or demographic factor (Table 3).

418 *Table 3.* Logistic regression models for punishment of the antisocial and neutral actors.

	Antisocial actor		Neutral actor	
	OR [95% CI]	p	OR [95% CI]	p
Anonymity (in-person)	0.49 [0.30, 0.80]	.005	0.91 [0.44, 1.87]	.807
Economic cost (costly)	0.40 [0.17, 0.87]	.026	0.65 [0.18, 1.86]	.457
Gender (boy)	0.73 [0.44, 1.18]	.196	0.86 [0.42, 1.75]	.686
Age	1.41 [1.21, 1.67]	<.001	0.93 [0.74, 1.17]	.565
$p(\Delta_{\text{deviance}})$ for addition of terms		.185		.904
Anonymity x Age	1.33 [0.97, 1.85]	.084	0.95 [0.60, 1.48]	.807
Gender x Age	1.11 [0.81, 1.51]	.528	1.09 [0.70, 1.69]	.711

419 **Note.** For the categorical predictors of anonymity, economic cost, and gender, for interpreting
 420 the odds ratios, the categories reported in parentheses are coded as 1. For age, the odds ratios
 421 indicate the effect of being one year older. Statistical significance is marked by bold type.

422

423 *Figure 2.* Probabilities of allocations to the antisocial and neutral actors, by economic cost and
 424 anonymity conditions. The values shown are the model predictions ($\pm 95\%$ CI) for a child of median
 425 age (6.6 years) from six logistic regression models of each type of allocation to each type of actor,
 426 with predictors age, economic cost, and anonymity.
 427

428

429

430 There was only a non-significant trend ($p < 0.1$) for the interaction between anonymity and age
 431 when predicting punishment in the original simple model (Table 3). However, visual inspection of an
 432 exploratory spline model (Figure 3) suggested that the effect of anonymity did indeed depend on age,
 433 but in a more complex way (RQ7), implying the original simple model does not adequately model
 434 age. The difference between the *in-person* and *anonymous conditions* was only clear for participants
 435 between about 5- and 7-years-old. The age effect was not moderated by gender (RQ8, Table 3).

436

437 *Figure 3.* Frequency of punishment of the antisocial actor, by age and anonymity. Points show *free-*
 438 *of-economic-cost condition* raw data means for each year-group. Lines show model fit ($\pm 95\%$ CI) in
 439 the *free-of-economic-cost condition*, from a model of all data with economic cost, anonymity, age,
 440 and the age * anonymity interaction entered together, where age was fitted using natural cubic splines
 441 (Durrleman & Simon, 1989; Hastie, 1992). In this method the data is split into sections (here, into
 442 three equal-sized samples by splitting at the age tertiles) and model coefficients are fit separately for
 443 each section, under the constraint that sections should join smoothly.

444

445 Allocation of good sweets (reward)

446 Rewarding the neutral actor with good sweets was common (Figure 2) and unaffected by any
 447 variable, except it increased slightly with age (Table 4). Rewarding the antisocial actor was
 448 surprisingly frequent – a child of median age does this roughly half the time when in person and free
 449 of economic cost (Figure 2). There were several significant predictors (Table 4). It was less common

450 in the *economically costly condition* (similarly to punishing). It decreased with age (in contrast to
 451 punishing, which increased). It was less common when anonymous (in contrast to punishing, which
 452 was more common when anonymous).

453 *Table 4. Logistic regression models for rewarding of the antisocial and neutral actors.*

	Antisocial actor		Neutral actor	
	OR [95% CI]	<i>p</i>	OR [95% CI]	<i>p</i>
Anonymity (in-person)	2.09 [1.27, 3.48]	.004	0.72 [0.42, 1.23]	.230
Economic cost (costly)	0.43 [0.20, 0.89]	.026	0.53 [0.26, 1.09]	.081
Gender (boy)	1.46 [0.88, 2.41]	.141	1.49 [0.87, 2.56]	.149
Age	0.67 [0.56, 0.79]	<.001	1.29 [1.08, 1.57]	.007
$p(\Delta_{\text{deviance}})$ for addition of terms		.015		.436
Anonymity x Age	0.70 [0.49, 0.98]	.042	1.19 [0.83, 1.71]	.342
Gender x Age	0.69 [0.49, 0.96]	.031	0.86 [0.60, 1.22]	.395

454 **Note.** For the categorical predictors of anonymity, economic cost, and gender, for interpreting
 455 the odds ratios, the categories reported in parentheses are coded as 1. For age, the odds ratios
 456 indicate the effect of being one year older. Statistical significance is marked by bold type.
 457

458 Additional exploration prompted by the surprisingly high frequency of rewarding of the antisocial
 459 actor indicated that it was connected to the rare behaviour of punishing the neutral actor: the antisocial
 460 actor was rewarded by 69% of the 35 participants who punished the neutral actor, compared to 30%
 461 of the 268 participants who did not. A new model of reward of the antisocial actor was therefore
 462 constructed, containing all the original predictors listed in Table 4, and as an additional predictor,
 463 punishment of the neutral actor. The addition improved the model, $p(\Delta_{\text{deviance}}) < .001$, with punishment
 464 of the neutral actor a significant predictor, OR = 6.4, 95% CI = [2.9, 15.1], $p < .001$.

465 Most younger children rewarded the antisocial actor, but the behaviour decreased considerably
 466 with age (Table 4, Figure 4). The effect of anonymity depended on age, only applying to children in
 467 the middle age group, between approximately 5- and 7-years-old (Table 4, Figure 4a). This mirrored
 468 the previously presented effect of anonymity on punishment, except that whereas anonymity
 469 increased punishment of the antisocial actor, it decreased rewarding. There was also a tendency for
 470 the reduction with age in rewarding the antisocial actor to be different for boys and girls (Table 4),
 471 with the behaviour more common in young boys than young girls in the lower age group (between
 472 approximately 4- and 6-years-old) but reducing faster in boys (Figure 4b).

473

474 *Figure 4.* Frequency of rewarding of the antisocial actor, by (a) age and anonymity, and (b) age and
 475 gender. Points show raw data means for each year-group. Lines show model fit ($\pm 95\%$ CI) from
 476 models of all data with each of the two predictors plus their interaction. For age and anonymity, as
 477 for the analysis displayed in Figure 3, because the simple original model fit less well, a spline model
 478 was fit, in the same way.

479

480 Cross-cultural and cross-community comparisons

481 Quantitative cross-cultural comparison was possible due to the availability of Swedish data
 482 collected with a very similar method (Figure 2 of Kenward & Östh, 2015). We compared only
 483 punishment, because in the Swedish data, rewarding was more difficult to interpret, as there was no
 484 option to allocate an empty box. Moreover, since the Swedish study manipulated social cost but not
 485 economic cost, cross-cultural comparisons between Vanuatu and Sweden were conducted using only
 486 ni-Vanuatu data from the *free-of-economic-cost condition*. Because the age range of the Swedish
 487 sample was narrow, but the Vanuatu age range was wide, we compared Vanuatu model-prediction
 488 proportions with Swedish raw data proportions. Visual inspection of the almost entirely overlapping
 489 confidence intervals indicates that the two samples were similar, with undetected differences likely
 490 to be small (RQ10, Figure 5). (We therefore omit calculation of p -values, which are complex to derive
 491 for a comparison of raw data with model predictions.)

492

493 *Figure 5.* Cross-cultural comparison of punishment of antisocial and neutral actors, by anonymity
 494 condition. Swedish data are sample means ($\pm 95\%$ CI) for the narrow age-range sample of mean 5.2
 495 years (data from Kenward & Östh, 2015, *free-of-economic-cost*). Vanuatu data are model fits ($\pm 95\%$
 496 CI) at the same age and in the *free-of-economic-cost condition*, from models of all data with condition,
 497 cost, age, and the anonymity * age interaction as predictors.

498

499 The rural and urban ni-Vanuatu samples also did not have matched age distributions. Further, the
 500 rural sample (all in the *free-of-economic-cost* and *anonymous condition*) was too small on its own (n
 501 = 21) for multivariate modelling. This comparison was therefore enabled by creation of a sub-sample
 502 of urban children (in the *free-of-economic-cost* and *anonymous condition*) that was age-matched with
 503 the rural sample (see Robbins & Rochat, 2011, Study 6 for a similar approach in a similar context).
 504 Each rural child was matched with the urban child nearest in age but not yet added to the comparison
 505 subsample, and these 21 matched urban children were then added to the comparison subsample. This
 506 matching procedure was repeated four times, yielding an urban subsample ($n = 84$) suitable for
 507 comparison because mean, maximum, and minimum age in years were the same to one decimal place
 508 as the rural sample (mean = 7.3, range = 5.5 to 9.9).

509 Comparing these age-matched rural and urban samples indicated no evidence for a difference in
 510 tendency for urban and rural children to punish or reward the antisocial or neutral actor (RQ11), as
 511 illustrated by overlapping confidence intervals indicating that undetected differences were unlikely
 512 to be large (Figure 6).

513

514 *Figure 6.* Punishment and reward by rural children and an age-matched urban subsample in the *free-*
 515 *of-economic-cost* and *anonymous* condition. Values are sample means ($\pm 95\%$ CI).

516

Discussion

517 The present study investigated how ni-Vanuatu children respond to norm violations, with a
 518 particular focus on how economic and social costs shape 3PP and reward decisions, and on whether
 519 behavioural patterns observed in previous studies of WEIRD populations generalised to the Vanuatu
 520 context. Overall, the results largely supported our original predictions, while also revealing several
 521 unanticipated results concerning rewarding of the antisocial actor that warrant further consideration.
 522 We found relatively high levels of 3PP by middle childhood, increasing with age; clear selectivity of
 523 punishment target (antisocial actor over neutral actor); sensitivity to both economic and social costs;
 524 and no evidence of cross-cultural or community differences. These results were very much not in line
 525 with those of a recent study conducted in the same populations at the same time (McAuliffe et al.,
 526 2025), which found relatively low levels of 3PP, in part because of very low levels of 3PP in rural
 527 compared to urban children, with rates of punishment and target-selectivity decreasing with age, and
 528 no sensitivity to economic cost.

529 Punishment of norm violations

530 Consistent with a substantial body of developmental research (e.g., Hamlin et al., 2011; House et
531 al., 2020; Jordan et al., 2014; Kenward & Östh, 2015; Lee et al., 2024; McAuliffe et al., 2015, 2025;
532 Yudkin et al., 2020), ni-Vanuatu children preferentially punished the norm violator (i.e., antisocial
533 actor) relative to the individual following social norms (i.e., neutral actor). This tendency emerged
534 reliably by five years of age (age range: 4-11 years), in line with findings reported by Kenward and
535 Östh (2015) in a Swedish sample. In a different sample (but overlapping population) of ni-Vanuatu
536 children, McAuliffe et al. (2025) similarly observed preferential punishment of selfish over fair
537 distributors between 7 and 11 years (age range: 7-13 years). In that study, however, older ni-Vanuatu
538 children (11-13 years) were less likely to distinguish between selfish and fair distributors when they
539 punished. Our sample did not extend into this older age range.

540 Whilst House et al. (2020) also documented selective 3PP towards norm violators in both WEIRD
541 (US and Germany) and non-WEIRD populations (Argentina and India), their estimates suggested a
542 later emergence of this bias, around 9-10 years of age. Importantly, this difference in timing between
543 House et al.'s (2020) and our study is likely attributable to methodological rather than cultural
544 differences – children in their study were exposed to a variety of primes, some of which may have
545 reduced selectivity. Taken together, these studies converge in showing that, across diverse cultural
546 contexts, children tend to allocate 3PP selectively rather than indiscriminately, while indicating that
547 the emergence of this selectivity is sensitive to context.

548 As predicted, both economic and social costs reduced ni-Vanuatu children's likelihood of
549 punishing the antisocial actor. Children were less likely to engage in 3PP when it required sacrificing
550 part of their own sweet endowment, and when it had to be delivered in person rather than
551 anonymously. These results closely parallel previous findings from WEIRD child samples (effect of
552 social cost in Sweden: Kenward & Östh, 2015; effect of economic cost in the US and Canada:
553 McAuliffe et al., 2015, 2025), providing converging evidence that children, like adults, are sensitive

554 to both economic (Lewisch et al., 2011; Fan et al., 2013) and social costs associated with punishment
555 (Molho et al., 2020; Molho & Wu, 2021). The replication of these cost effects in Vanuatu supports
556 the view that children's punitive behaviour is shaped at least in part by strategic cost-benefit
557 considerations and self-serving motives rather than reflecting a purely altruistic or unconditional
558 motivation to enforce norms (Baumard, 2010; Guala, 2012).

559 Notably, our economic cost results appear to be at odds with those reported by McAuliffe et al.
560 (2025) in Vanuatu, who found that ni-Vanuatu children were equally likely to punish selfish
561 distributors regardless of whether 3PP was free or economically costly. Differences in sample
562 composition and statistical power between the two studies may account for this discrepancy.
563 McAuliffe et al.'s (2025) sample contained approximately twice as many rural as urban children, and
564 rural children in their study exhibited very low overall rates of 3PP. This may have resulted in floor
565 effects that limited the detection of cost-condition differences. In contrast, our sample not only
566 contained many more urban than rural children but was also more than twice the size of that of
567 McAuliffe et al. (2025), providing greater statistical power. It is also possible that urban children are
568 more sensitive to economic cost than rural children in Vanuatu.

569 Moreover, exploratory analyses revealed that the effect of social cost on 3PP was age-dependent
570 among ni-Vanuatu children (although no a priori prediction was made regarding interactions between
571 age and social cost of 3PP). Specifically, delivering 3PP in person reduced punishment rates mainly
572 among children in the intermediate age range (approximately 5-7 years), with weaker or absent effects
573 in younger and older children. This pattern suggests that sensitivity to social cost may peak during
574 middle childhood, when children begin to form social relationships outside the family and become
575 increasingly attentive to feedback from others (Engelmann & Rapp, 2018). Children in this age range
576 may therefore be especially motivated to avoid acquiring a reputation as punishers while building
577 their social support network. Notably, traditional models posit this kind of reputation management as
578 involving the monitoring of others' beliefs and evaluations of oneself and therefore assumed to
579 depend on theory of mind (Banerjee, 2002). Ni-Vanuatu children show lower performance than age-

580 matched Australian children in theory of mind tasks, but this might also depend on cultural norms
581 which deprecate discussion of others' minds (Dixson et al., 2018).

582 3PP rates of the antisocial actor were relatively high and increased with age in our sample of ni-
583 Vanuatu children, in line with nearly all prior developmental findings (House et al., 2020; Jordan et
584 al., 2014; McAuliffe et al., 2015; Salali et al., 2015). In contrast, McAuliffe et al. (2025) reported that
585 3PP rates of selfish distributors decreased with age in their sample of ni-Vanuatu children (but in none
586 of the other cultures they studied). The apparent inconsistency between these studies in Vanuatu likely
587 reflects differences in how children respond to distinct types of moral violations – aggressive property
588 destruction in our study, compared with unfair resource allocation in McAuliffe et al.'s (2025) study.
589 The developmental trajectory of 3PP for unfairness may differ from that for antisocial behaviour
590 because ni-Vanuatu culture places greater emphasis on proper social conduct than fair resource
591 distribution – churlishness and bullying are seen as more serious than opportunistic consumption of
592 food or wealth items (Dixson, 2016). In this sense, 3PP rates may be indicative of the importance
593 attributed to specific moral violations. Following this interpretation, the longer ni-Vanuatu children
594 are socialised to local cultural norms, the more likely they would be to punish antisocial actors (as
595 observed in the present study) and the less likely they would be to punish unfair distributors (as
596 reported by McAuliffe et al., 2025). A similar account has been proposed to explain divergent
597 developmental patterns in 3PP of unfairness vs. group disloyalty in British, Colombian and Spanish
598 children (Arini et al., 2021, 2025).

599 No gender differences in 3PP rates were detected in ni-Vanuatu children, contrasting with earlier
600 findings in WEIRD samples showing that Swedish boys engaged in 3PP more often than their female
601 counterparts, within a very similar experimental paradigm (Kenward & Östh, 2015). Moreover, age
602 did not moderate any effect of gender on 3PP behaviour, indicating that boys and girls in Vanuatu did
603 not differ in 3PP behaviour at any age. The absence of 3PP gender differences in the ni-Vanuatu
604 sample is consistent with a growing body of evidence suggesting that behavioural gender differences

605 are influenced by the socio-economic environment, with differences tending to be smaller in less
606 economically developed countries (Falk & Hermle, 2018).

607 Contrary to predictions derived from experimental and ethnographic work on the links between
608 community group size and 3PP rates (Henrich et al., 2006; Marlowe et al., 2008), we found no
609 evidence that urban ni-Vanuatu children punished antisocial actors more frequently than rural
610 children. This pattern aligns with a large-scale cross-cultural developmental study (Kanngiesser et
611 al., 2022), which reported enforcement of conventional norms across eight societies, with variation
612 in rates not explained by community size. By contrast, McAuliffe et al. (2025) found significant
613 urban-rural differences in Vanuatu, with urban children punishing selfish distributors at higher rates
614 than rural children. However, a limitation of McAuliffe et al. (2025)'s study is that urbanicity was
615 confounded with age, as urban children were predominantly younger and rural children
616 predominantly older. That said, this age difference was probably not enough to entirely account for
617 the strong difference in 3PP rates they observed between rural and urban samples. Further, our urban
618 vs. rural comparison is underpowered due to a low rural sample size. Compatible with all available
619 evidence is that children's 3PP tendencies are lower in rural than urban Vanuatu, but not as strongly
620 as indicated by McAuliffe et al. (2025)'s sample, at least not in the context of antisocial behaviour
621 rather than unfairness.

622 3PP rates in our urban ni-Vanuatu sample closely resembled those observed in the (urban)
623 Swedish sample tested by Kenward and Östh (2015). Likewise, 3PP rates of selfish distributors were
624 fairly similar in urban children from the US, Argentina, Germany and India, with no substantial
625 differences across countries (House et al., 2020). This is also in line with findings from a study with
626 adult participants showing that punishment of economic free-riding was comparable across 16 cities
627 worldwide, despite variation in cultural and economic contexts (Herrmann et al., 2008). By contrast,
628 the Global Preference Survey indicates that looser kinship structure (as in Sweden, with 0.2%
629 extended family co-residence; Iacovou & Skew, 2011) predicts higher willingness to use 3PP to
630 respond to injustice, compared to people from societies with tighter kinship structure (as in Vanuatu,

631 with 24% extended family co-residence; Vanuatu Household Income and Expenditure Survey, 2010)
632 (Enke, 2019). There are many confounding variables – for example, the Global Preference Survey
633 captures abstract self-reports of normative preferences, whereas the present study, Kenward and Östh
634 (2015), House et al. (2020) and Herrmann et al. (2008) examined actual behaviour with real costs
635 (whether social or economic). More data will be required to resolve these issues.

636 Patterns of rewarding, including potential appeasement behaviour

637 Analyses of reward behaviour were exploratory, but they revealed highly suggestive patterns.
638 Rewarding the neutral actor was common in our ni-Vanuatu sample, and increased with age, mirroring
639 the developmental pattern observed for 3PP of the antisocial actor. Surprisingly, rewarding the
640 antisocial actor was also relatively common, although less so than rewarding the neutral actor. Reward
641 rates of the antisocial actor were particularly high among younger children and declined with age.
642 There were detectable gender differences, with boys rewarding the antisocial actor more often than
643 girls, but only within the youngest age group (approximately 4-6 years). Moreover, whereas economic
644 cost had similar effects on 3PP and reward of the antisocial actor, reducing children's likelihood of
645 engaging in both behaviours, anonymity had opposite effects: it increased 3PP but decreased
646 rewarding of the antisocial actor. Notably, these effects of anonymity were age-dependent for both
647 rewarding and 3PP, emerging only among children in the intermediate age range (approximately 5-7
648 years), but not among younger and older children.

649 One likely interpretation of these patterns is that some children in our ni-Vanuatu sample
650 perceived the antisocial actor as a dominant individual and chose to appease them. There is indeed
651 evidence that toddlers treat antisocial behaviours as cues to dominance (Gülgöz & Gelman, 2017).
652 For instance, behaviours such as destroying someone's belongings – as in our experimental protocol
653 – may be interpreted in this way. Based on these cues, toddlers infer who is likely to prevail in future
654 interactions (Bas & Sebastian-Galles, 2021; Mascaro & Csibra, 2012), to be obeyed (Margoni et al.,
655 2018), and to receive preferential access to resources (Enright et al., 2017). Toddlers also integrate

656 social status information into their own behaviour, by approaching dominant and avoiding
657 subordinate individuals (Thomas et al., 2016), similarly to what has been observed in adult bonobos
658 (Krupenye & Hare, 2018), humans' closest living relatives (together with chimpanzees). In
659 preschoolers, coercive behaviour is part of what makes individuals attractive as play partners
660 (Hawley, 2003). Swedish four-year-olds strategically allocate resources to rich rather than poor
661 recipients when they anticipate a potential for future reciprocity (Kenward et al., 2015). Interestingly,
662 it has been found that, when children are asked to distribute resources between a dominant and a
663 subordinate individual, 3- and 4-year-olds favour the dominant, 5-year-olds show no preference, and
664 8-year-olds favour the subordinate (Charafeddine et al., 2016). This shift could be due to
665 developmental changes in how children evaluate dominant individuals, possibly driven by an
666 increasing understanding of the emotional impact of antisocial behaviour (Charafeddine et al., 2016).
667 This developmental shift is very much in line with the age-related decline in rewarding the antisocial
668 actor observed in ni-Vanuatu children.

669 Such appeasement behaviour can be adaptive, as dominance is often associated with control over
670 resources and social influence (Book et al., 2012). Appeasers might obtain a share or at least avoid
671 being the target of further coercion. Such considerations may be particularly salient for younger
672 children, who are highly attuned to power asymmetries and may be especially motivated to appease
673 antisocial individuals (Charafeddine et al., 2016). The finding that anonymity reduced reward but
674 increased 3PP of the antisocial actor among ni-Vanuatu children fits this account well. If rewarding
675 the antisocial actor signals affiliation, this incentive would be diminished when the antisocial actor
676 will not know of the appeaser. Conversely, anonymity likely reduces the perceived risk of retaliation
677 when punishing the antisocial actor (Kenward & Östh, 2015).

678 These findings may appear at odds with recent evidence suggesting that children's punishment
679 and reward behaviours are insensitive to anticipated future interactions (Lee et al., 2024). In that
680 study, children punished unfair distributors and rewarded fair distributors, at comparable rates
681 irrespective of whether the same or a different individual would later distribute resources to them.

682 This led the authors to conclude that children enforce fairness norms in a principled way rather than
683 for self-interested, strategic reasons. Importantly, however, in Lee et al.'s (2024) study, children
684 interacted with distributors of their same age, anonymously and through a computer game, whereas
685 here, children in the *in-person condition* were told they would have a face-to-face interaction with an
686 antisocial adult. Our situation appears more realistic, and our result converges with previous findings
687 that already from four-years-old, children frequently make resource allocations from a perspective of
688 strategic self-interest (Kenward et al., 2015).

689 Lastly, another suggestive result emerging from our exploratory analyses is the association
690 between reward of the antisocial actor and 3PP of the neutral actor. Although punishment of the
691 neutral actor was a rare (yet not negligible) occurrence in our ni-Vanuatu sample, it was a significant
692 predictor of reward of the antisocial actor. Specifically, the few children who punished the neutral
693 actor, compared to the many who did not, were more likely to reward the antisocial actor. The
694 coupling of these behaviours suggests that, for a small subset of children in our sample, reward of the
695 antisocial actor and punishment of the neutral actor may be different expressions of the same
696 underlying motive to achieve social status.

697 This interpretation derives from the adult literature, which has shown that people enacting
698 punishment may evoke fear, thereby building a reputation as aggressive (Eriksson et al., 2016; Gordon
699 et al., 2014). Thus, punishment may be used as a competitive strategy to assert dominance, to the
700 detriment of the punished individuals (Redhead et al., 2020; Sylwester et al., 2013). This goal may
701 be more easily achieved by punishing individuals who appear inoffensive, such as the neutral actor
702 in our experiment – a behaviour that can be considered a form of antisocial punishment (Herrmann
703 et al., 2008). Of note, antisocial punishment is especially pronounced in conditions of resource
704 scarcity (Prediger et al., 2014), and in low-income countries (Herrmann et al., 2008). Based on this
705 evidence, we speculate that the minority of ni-Vanuatu children who were most motivated to pursue
706 social power may have engaged in two complementary behaviours: rewarding powerful, antisocial

707 individuals to gain the benefits of affiliation, and punishing relatively weak individuals to assert their
708 own social standing.

709 Limitations, future directions, and general conclusions

710 Our study focuses on the social cost of punishment, in addition to examining economic costs,
711 which arguably represent a less realistic operationalisation of the costs of 3PP. However, for practical
712 and ethical reasons, social costs are more challenging to examine, and there may be imperfections in
713 our social cost manipulation, which was not subject to a manipulation check. It is possible that the
714 diminished response to the social cost manipulation in the oldest children (leading to an inverse U-
715 shaped response with age to that manipulation) is because older children are not convinced that they
716 will meet antisocial individuals in person.

717 Our rural sample and our sample in the *economically costly condition* are both small. Effects of
718 economic cost were anyway detected, but the confidence intervals for behaviours in rural children
719 are compatible with moderate undetected differences between the rural and urban sample, in line with
720 McAuliffe et al. (2025).

721 Since we provide important evidence that children are highly sensitive to both economic and
722 social costs, and capable of strategic cost-benefit calculations when deciding how to respond to social
723 norm violations, future studies might examine the cognitive underpinnings of these strategic decisions
724 and their reputational and social consequences. In adults, activation of the dorsal anterior cingulate
725 cortex is higher when administering costly rather than non-costly 3PP (Qu et al., 2018). Because this
726 brain region is implicated in monitoring cognitive conflict (Botvinick et al., 2004), it has been
727 suggested that the higher the cost of 3PP, the higher people's cognitive conflict between their self-
728 interest and their desire to enforce social norms (Cheng et al., 2022). It remains to be understood
729 whether these patterns are affected by age.

730 It would be interesting to investigate whether children's decisions to engage in costly 3PP of norm
731 violators influence how they are perceived and treated by their peers. If punishment is primarily

732 viewed as an expression of aggression and formidability (Eriksson et al., 2016; Gordon, et al., 2014),
733 children who punish may be seen as more dominant and threatening. On one hand, this may
734 discourage their peers from attempting to take advantage of them; on the other hand, peers may also
735 avoid or exclude them from social interactions out of fear. Conversely, if punishment is perceived as
736 an altruistic act aimed at preventing harm to others, children who punish may experience positive
737 social outcomes, such as being preferred as social partners or entrusted with greater resources, as has
738 been observed in adults (Nelissen, 2008). More naturalistic studies can be key for answering these
739 questions (Hawley, 2003).

740 Taken together, the results of this and other studies (House et al., 2020; McAuliffe et al., 2025)
741 provide evidence that across many cultures, children use 3PP to selectively target norm violators, that
742 3PP is sensitive to social and economic costs, and that its frequency increases with age, with most
743 children engaging by middle childhood. Here, selectivity was seen by the age of 5. Prior to this study,
744 Vanuatu represented the prime exception to this age-related increase in 3PP rates, which otherwise
745 has been found in every studied culture (although Uganda also showed some important exceptions,
746 McAuliffe et al., 2025). Early development of tendencies towards 3PP may be human universal. At
747 the same time, the prevalence of reward responses to antisocial individuals, and cultural difference in
748 norm enforcement development observed in other studies (Kanngiesser et al., 2022; McAuliffe et al.,
749 2025), raise important questions about how culturally evolved punishment behaviours interact with
750 core cognitive and motivational processes during development.

751 Open Practices

752 All raw data, analysis code in R, and method details are openly available on a public GitHub
753 repository (Anon, 2026), and a permanent snapshot will be archived on Zenodo following review.

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